

Original article

Knowledge of autologous blood donation among healthcare workers in a tertiary healthcare facility in Northeastern Nigeria.

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Abstract

Background: Blood transfusion is essential in healthcare, but ensuring a safe and sufficient supply is difficult, especially in low-resource settings. Autologous blood donation (ABD) offers advantages to safety and conservation, yet its use is limited by knowledge gaps among healthcare workers and various infrastructural constraints. This study assessed healthcare workers' knowledge of ABD in a tertiary facility in Azare. **Materials and Methods:** The study employed a cross-sectional design at the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare, involving 237 doctors, nurses, and medical laboratory scientists selected through stratified random sampling. A structured, pre-tested questionnaire validated by experts, with a reliability score of 0.7, was used to assess knowledge of autologous blood donation. Ethical approval was obtained, and data collection adhered to strict ethical standards. Analysis was conducted using SPSS version 26. **Results:** A total of 237 healthcare workers participated (68.3% nurses/midwives, 24.9% doctors, 6.8% medical laboratory scientists), with a mean age of 32.97 ± 9.6 years. Overall awareness of autologous blood donation (ABD) was 78.9%. Knowledge of ABD, its definition, role in reducing transfusion-transmissible infections, methods, and eligibility criteria differed significantly by professional cadre (Fisher's Exact tests, $p = 0.0001$), with doctors demonstrating higher knowledge levels than other groups. **Conclusion:** Healthcare workers in Azare demonstrated a high level of awareness of autologous blood donation, with doctors and laboratory scientists showing the strongest understanding of its principles and benefits. Targeted educational initiatives for nursing staff are recommended to ensure uniform knowledge across cadres, strengthen transfusion safety, and promote optimal use of autologous blood.

Keywords: Autologous blood donation, Healthcare workers, Knowledge, Tertiary Healthcare Facility

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Introduction

Blood transfusion is a vital part of modern healthcare, supporting care from emergencies to the treatment of chronic anaemia. However, many regions, especially low- and middle-income countries, struggle to ensure a safe and reliable blood supply.¹ In recent years, innovations and reforms have been introduced to address these challenges.² Innovative approaches such as drone-based blood delivery, walking blood banks, and intraoperative auto-transfusion are also being explored to improve access and reduce wastage in resource-limited settings.³ Health systems are increasingly adopting patient blood

management strategies to optimise blood use and reduce unnecessary transfusions.⁴

Despite these advances, challenges persist in blood utilisation. For instance, a 2025 study in a Taiwanese hospital reported ongoing blood component wastage, highlighting the need for efficiency across recruitment, collection, storage, distribution, and use.⁵ In African contexts, systemic barriers such as limited infrastructure, inadequate human resources, and fragmented blood services further compromise transfusion safety and supply.⁶

Autologous blood donation (ABD) offers significant benefits, including reducing alloimmunization and transfusion-transmitted infections and conserving community blood supplies by allowing patients to use their own stored blood.⁷ However, ABD also carries risks, such as iatrogenic anaemia, volume overload, and administrative errors, and poses logistical and economic challenges, particularly in low-resource settings.⁷⁻⁹

Autologous blood donation (ABD), an important component of patient blood management, is variably utilised worldwide but remains particularly valuable in selected settings. For example, recent evidence (2025) indicates that prepartum ABD can be performed safely, with low transfusion requirements when supported by well-organised and competent blood transfusion services.¹⁰ While high-income countries benefit from robust blood services and access to advanced autotransfusion techniques, many low- and middle-income countries still face gaps in collection, testing, and clinical practice, limiting large-scale ABD implementation.^{11,12}

In Nigeria, blood transfusion practices are shaped by policy, infrastructure, and clinical demand, with tertiary hospitals relying on replacement and family donors; these local operational barriers and inconsistent clinician uptake mirror global challenges, where limited training and resources hinder the widespread adoption of autologous donation and cell-salvage strategies.^{13,14} Globally, clinicians' limited training in transfusion medicine contributes to inappropriate transfusions, overuse of allogeneic blood, and underutilization of conservation strategies like autologous donation and cell salvage.^{15,16} Addressing this requires effective patient blood management, with coordinated teamwork among clinical, laboratory, and blood-bank staff and transfusion committees to ensure safe donor

selection, processing, transfusion, and haemovigilance.^{15,17,18}

Assessing healthcare workers' knowledge toward autologous blood donation (ABD) is essential, as they play a pivotal role in recommending, counseling, and implementing ABD within safe transfusion and patient-blood management practices. Evidence shows that knowledge gaps can hinder the uptake of safer blood alternatives, especially in resource-limited settings, making local data from Azare crucial for guiding targeted training, policy development, and strategies to improve ABD utilisation and transfusion safety.

Healthcare workers' knowledge directly determines ABD recommendation and implementation, with gaps undermining programme uptake.¹⁵ Integrating ABD into PBM reduces reliance on allogeneic units and improves patient outcomes, making HCW's knowledge of ABD essential for effective blood resource optimisation.^{15,19} Recent multi-centre assessments of Nigerian tertiary hospitals documented ongoing shortages, reliance on replacement donors, and variable adoption of blood-conservation strategies. Local HCW knowledge is a modifiable factor that could help address these gaps.¹³ Nigerian surgeons and hospital staff are willing to use autologous techniques, but equipment, protocols, and training gaps highlight the need to assess knowledge for targeted interventions.^{20,21} Published KAP work on blood donation frequently shows good knowledge but low practice; there is little published evidence specific to ABD among HCWs in Azare, so this study will fill an important local evidence gap to inform policy and interventions.^{22,23}

Hence, the study aimed to assess Knowledge of Autologous Blood Donation among Healthcare Workers in a Tertiary Healthcare Facility in Northeastern Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Study area

The study was conducted at the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare (FUHSTHA), Bauchi State, in North-Eastern Nigeria. The facility was initially established as the Federal Medical Centre in 2000 following the federal government's takeover of a long-standing general hospital that had served the community for over six decades. In 2024, it was upgraded to a teaching hospital and became affiliated with the Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare (FUHSA), founded in 2021.

FUHSTHA comprises 26 departments, grouped into administrative/non-clinical units (10) and clinical/medical units (16). The clinical departments include Accident and Emergency, Dental Services, General Outpatient (GOPD), Internal Medicine, MAC Secretariat, Medical Library, NHIS Office, Nursing Services, Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Ophthalmology, Paediatrics, Pathology, Pharmacy, Physiotherapy, Radiology, and Surgery. The hospital provides services to all senatorial districts in Bauchi State, as well as neighbouring states such as Yobe and Jigawa. It began operations in 2001 with 152 beds, expanding to 412 beds by its 20th anniversary in 2022.

FUHSTHA provides comprehensive healthcare services, including emergencies, routine, and specialised care, as well as diagnostics, treatment, training, and research. As both a healthcare provider and academic institution, it plays a key role in northeastern Nigeria. For this study, research monitoring was conducted across the clinical, nursing, and pathology departments to ensure adherence to the study protocol and to maintain high data quality.

Study design

The study used a prospective cross-sectional design, with structured questionnaires administered to the study subjects. The study was carried out over a one-month period, from 1st to 31st August 2025, in the nursing, pathology, and clinical departments of the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare, Bauchi State.

Study population

The study included healthcare workers at the Federal University of Health Science, medical doctors (consultants, medical officers, residents, and house officers), nurses and midwives, and medical laboratory scientists who were directly or indirectly involved in blood transfusion, preoperative preparation, or surgical care. Healthcare workers outside these cadres or on leave during the study period were excluded.

Sample size/sampling technique

Sample size was calculated using the formula for descriptive studies:²⁴

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \times p \times (1-p)}{d^2}$$

Where:

n= minimum sample size

Z=Z-score (1.96 at 95% CI)

p= assumed prevalence (50% if unknown)

d=margin of error (0.05)

Substituting the values:

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.5(1-0.5)}{(0.05)^2} = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.25}{0.0025} = 384.16$$

Thus, the initial sample size for the study was 384 healthcare workers. However, because the total number of HCWs in FUHSTHA was finite, estimated at 547 (137 doctors, 371 nurses, and 39 laboratory scientists), the finite population correction (FPC) was applied to adjust the sample size. The corrected sample size (nf) was then calculated using the formula:²⁴

$$nf = \frac{n}{1 + \left(\frac{n-1}{N}\right)}$$

Where:

n=384 is the initial sample size,

N=547 is the total population of HCWs in FUHSTHA,

nf is the adjusted sample size after applying the FPC.

Substituting the values:

$$nf = \frac{384}{1 + \left(\frac{383}{547}\right)} = \frac{384}{1.700} \approx 226$$

$$\text{Attrition rate } n_2 = 226 \times \frac{10}{100} = 22.6 \approx 23$$

Therefore, the final adjusted sample size for this study was 226 + 23 = 249 healthcare workers, ensuring both statistical accuracy and resource efficiency in data collection.

Sampling technique

The technique used was stratified random sampling, in which strata categorised healthcare workers into doctors, nurses, and medical laboratory scientists. Then, proportionate sampling was employed to ensure fair representation of various subgroups of health workers within the population of the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital, Azare, (FUHSTHA). The healthcare workers were divided into 3 proportions based on professional cadre. Doctors: 137, Nurses and midwives: 371, Medical laboratory scientists:39.

Total population (N): 137 + 371 + 39 =547

Calculating the proportions

- Doctors: 137/547=0.2505
- Nurses and midwives: 371/547=0.6781
- Medical laboratory scientist: 39/547=0.0713

Applying the proportions to the sample size (n=249)

- Doctors: 0.2505 × 249 = 62.37 ≈62
- Nurses and midwives: 0.6781 × 249= 168.84 ≈ 169
- Medical laboratory scientist: 0.0713 × 249 = 17.75 ≈ 18

Finally, 249 healthcare workers were selected from a total of 547 using a simple random sampling (SRS) technique and were administered questionnaires. However, 12 selected participants were unavailable due to leave (2 medical laboratory scientists, 3 doctors, and 7 nurses).

Consequently, data were obtained from 237 healthcare workers and included in the analysis.

Study instrument

The study questionnaire was developed using a thorough review of relevant literature, World Health Organisation (WHO) recommendations, and established transfusion medicine guidelines on autologous blood donation.^{17,25-27} The primary data collection tool for this study was a structured, self-administered questionnaire, designed to assess Knowledge, and consisted of two parts. Socio-demographics and on knowledge comprising of yes/ no/don't know and multiple-choice to choose all that were applicable items that evaluated the respondents' understanding of types, indications, benefits, and safety of ABD.¹⁷

A pilot study was conducted at the Federal Medical Centre, Misau, Bauchi State, involving 24 healthcare personnel, representing 10% of the total sample size, and comprising 6 doctors, 16 nurses, and 2 medical laboratory scientists. The selection was using simple random sampling. Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.7 was calculated using a pilot study sample. This also assessed the reliability of the research instrument.

Face validity was assessed by subject experts in transfusion medicine, public health and pre-tested on HCWs in the pilot study, assessing the relevance, coverage, and appropriateness of each item to the study objective. Feedback from experts and pilot participants was utilised to refine the questionnaire, enhance clarity, eliminate ambiguous terms, and ensure that the instrument effectively measured the intended knowledge on autologous blood donation. Potential confounders such as age, sex, professional cadre, years of experience, prior training in transfusion medicine, or exposure to ABD are identified during study design or data collection.

Data collection

A structured, pre-tested, self-administered paper-based questionnaire was used to collect data on knowledge regarding ABD. The questionnaire was distributed to selected participants using simple random sampling across the clinical, laboratory, and nursing departments. Before administration, participants were briefed on the purpose, and informed consent was obtained. Participation was voluntary, and data collection was conducted over one month.

Collected data was securely stored in password-protected digital files and coded to ensure participant anonymity.

Data analysis

The completed questionnaires were compiled, cleaned, and analysed using SPSS (Statistical

Package for Social Sciences) version 26 (IBM® SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to summarise socio-demographic characteristics and the distribution of knowledge levels among respondents.

Inferential statistics were performed using the Chi-square (χ^2) test to evaluate the association between healthcare workers' level of knowledge on autologous blood donation and professional cadre. Statistical significance was defined at a threshold of $p \leq 0.05$

Ethical approval

Ethical approval was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee (HREC) of FUHSTHA (Approval No: NHREC/FUHSTHA/2024/11/11; approved 23rd July 2025). Participation was voluntary, confidentiality was maintained, and procedures were aligned with the Declaration of Helsinki. Written informed consent was obtained from all respondents.

Results

A total of 237 healthcare workers participated in the study, comprising 16 medical laboratory scientists (6.8%), 59 doctors (24.9%), and 162 nurses/midwives (68.3%), as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Pie chart showing the Cadre of the participants

The mean age of the study participants is 32.97 ± 9.6 years with a range of 21 to 63 years. Their genders comprised 105 males (44.3%) and 132 females (55.7%). Marital status included 118 (49.8%) married, 114 (48.1%) single, 4 (1.7%) widows, and 1 (0.4%) widower. The nurses/midwives were from the nursing services department, the medical laboratory scientists from

the pathology department, and the doctors from the various hospital departments, as shown in Figure 2.

The nursing department accounted for 162 (68.4%) participants, while the departments of chemical pathology, urology, orthopaedics, and anaesthesia each had only one participant (1, 0.4%). Table 2 shows the responses of health workers on knowledge of ABD, and Table 3 shows the responses of HCWs to the methods and eligibility of ABD.

Figure 2: Bar chart showing the departments of the study participants.

Discussion

The mean age of the study participants was lower than the findings of Owghanda et al. (2021), in their study on health workers’ knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions of COVID in Port Harcourt, which reported 40.6±7.8 years.²⁸ This finding indicates that the bulk of healthcare workers involved in this study were young, reflecting the age structure of the health workforce in many Nigerian tertiary hospitals.

The study observed a predominance of nurses and midwives, reflecting the workforce distribution in most Nigerian tertiary health institutions, where nurses constitute the largest proportion of clinical staff.

This finding aligns with reports from the World Health Organisation and Ahmat et al. (2022) in the African region, where nurses represent the majority of the health workforce.^{29,30}

Table 1: Showing responses of health workers on knowledge of ABD

Cadre	Responses					
	<i>Have you heard of ABD?</i>			Total	Fisher’s Exact	P value
	Yes	No				
Doctors	59	0		59	33.38	0.0001
MLS	15	1		16		
Nurses/MW	113	49		162		
Total	187	50		237		
	<i>ABD involves donating one's blood for future use</i>					
	Yes	No	Don’t know	Total	Fisher’s Exact	P value
Doctors	59	0	0	59		
MLS	16	0	0	16	20.32	0.0001
Nurses	129	3	30	162		
Total	204	3	30	237		
	<i>Can ABD reduce the risk of TTIs?</i>					
	Yes	No	Don’t know	Total	Fisher’s Exact	P value
Doctors	59	0	0	59	20.00	0.0001
MLS	16	0	0	16		
Nurses	125	9	28	162		
Total	200	9	28	237		

The predominance of female respondents mirrors the gender distribution in Nigeria and other countries, where nursing and midwifery professions, largely dominated by women, comprise the largest share of clinical staff.^{31,32}

Most participants came from the Nursing Services Department, while the fewest were from Anaesthesia, Urology, Orthopaedics, and Chemical Pathology. This distribution reflects the staffing patterns of Nigerian tertiary hospitals, where nurses form the largest workforce, followed by medical doctors across clinical specialities, with comparatively fewer laboratory and allied health professionals.³³

When asked whether they had heard of autologous blood donation (ABD), all doctors responded

affirmatively, whereas some nurses reported not having heard of it. This aligns with findings from Tebabal et al. (2023) in Ethiopia, which showed that being a medical doctor was strongly associated with active participation in blood donation.³⁴ These results suggest that doctors are not only more knowledgeable about ABD but also more engaged in donation activities, which likely contributes to their higher level of understanding.

Table 2: Showing the differences in responses among health workers

Which of the methods of ABD do you know?				
<i>Methods</i>	Doctors	MLS	Nurses/Midwives	P-value
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	
1.Pre-operative donation	11	9	54	
2.Blood from relatives	0	0	24	
3.Intraoperative salvage	1	0	4	0.0001
4.Donating for others	0	0	40	
1 & 3	39	7	20	
1 & 4	4	0	5	
All of the above	4	0	15	
Total	59	16	162	
Who is eligible for ABD?				
<i>Eligibility</i>	Doctors	MLS	Nurses/Midwives	P-value
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	
1.Healthy surgical patient	6	0	29	
2.Patients with severe anaemia	1	0	22	
3.Pregnant women	0	1	5	0.0001
4.Patients with rare blood type	2	1	44	
1,3 &4	10	2	5	
1 & 4	37	12	49	
1,2 & 4	3	0	8	
Total	59	16	162	

For the statement, "ABD involves donating one's blood for future use," responses differed significantly across professional cadres. Doctors and medical laboratory scientists demonstrated very high conceptual awareness, whereas some nurses expressed uncertainty. This pattern mirrors findings from a 2023 study in Uganda by Usman et al., which also reported higher ABD understanding among physicians compared with nursing staff.²³ Physicians and medical laboratory staff consistently agree that pre-deposit autologous blood donation (ABD) reduces the risk of transfusion-transmitted

infections (TTIs), while most nurses share this view, though a notable minority remain uncertain or disagree. Evidence from clinical studies and recent reviews confirms that pre-deposit autologous donation effectively eliminates the risk of acquiring donor-derived viral infections, such as HIV, HBV, and HCV, from another person.^{12,19,35,36}

In response to the question, "Which method of ABD do you know?" doctors and medical laboratory scientists predominantly identified clinically recommended methods, such as preoperative autologous donation (PAD) and intraoperative cell

salvage, often citing both. In contrast, nurses more frequently listed a broader range of practices, including directed or relative donation and “donating for others”, reflecting conceptual differences and some confusion between true autologous donation and directed allogeneic donations.^{35,37}

Conclusion

This study demonstrates a generally high level of awareness of autologous blood donation (ABD) among healthcare workers in this tertiary healthcare facility, with nearly four out of five participants reporting prior knowledge of the concept. Doctors, in particular, showed strong and consistent understanding of ABD definition, its role in reducing transfusion-transmissible infections, appropriate methods, and eligibility criteria. Importantly, the professional cadre was significantly associated with knowledge level ($p = 0.0001$), indicating that clinical training and scope of practice positively influence comprehension of ABD.

Overall, the findings suggest a solid foundational awareness of ABD within the institution, especially among physicians, providing a favourable platform for targeted capacity-building initiatives to harmonise knowledge across all healthcare worker groups and strengthen patient blood management practices.

Recommendations

1. Provide targeted training for nurses by enhancing focused education on autologous blood donation (ABD) to reduce uncertainty and misconceptions among nursing staff.
2. Engage doctors and medical laboratory scientists as mentors to provide guidance, training, and advocacy on ABD practices specifically for nurses and other healthcare cadres.
3. Conduct regular workshops for all healthcare workers to provide consistent training on clinically recommended ABD methods, including preoperative autologous donation (PAD) and intraoperative cell salvage, ensuring uniform understanding and application.
4. Targeting healthcare workers, emphasise that ABD effectively reduces transfusion-transmitted infections to build their confidence and encourage wider adoption in clinical practice.

Limitations

1. Single-Centre Study: Conducted in only one tertiary healthcare facility, limiting generalizability to other hospitals or regions.
2. Cross-Sectional Design: Provides a snapshot of knowledge at one point in time; cannot establish causality or changes over time.
3. Self-Reported Data: Responses may be influenced by social desirability bias, with participants overestimating their knowledge.
4. Limited Depth of Assessment: Focused primarily on knowledge; may not fully capture practical skills, actual donation practices, or barriers to ABD implementation.
5. Potential Misinterpretation of ABD Concepts: Variations in understanding (e.g., confusion between autologous and directed donation) could affect the accuracy of responses.

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Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts of interest

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Concepts	X	X	X		X	
Design	X	X	X		X	
Definition of intellectual content	X	X	X	X	X	
Literature search	X	X		X	X	X
Clinical studies	X	X		X		X
Experimental studies	X		X	X		X